

Calibration of digital energy meters with IEC 61850-9-2 inputs

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Abstract—A system is developed for the absolute calibration of digital energy meters with IEC 61850-9-2 Sampled Value inputs. The meter under test is subjected to a stream of synthetically generated voltage and current samples simulating a poly-phase grid. Reading the meter before and after the test gives the accumulated energy. Comparing this value with a calculated value gives the error of the meter. This paper describes the error sources of digital energy meters and the test setup used to determine these errors. Small but nonzero errors in energy reading were found for some meters during tests that followed the tests defined in the IEC 62053-22.

Index Terms—Measurement techniques, Measurement uncertainty, Energy measurement, Substation automation, Smart grids

I. INTRODUCTION

Energy meters with digital inputs benefit from receiving measured instantaneous current and voltage values as Sampled Value (SV) streams. As a result, they eliminate issues associated with gain error, phase displacement, interference, and short- and long-term drifts inherent in analog signal processing chains. Despite this shift to digital processing, the concept of metering accuracy classes remains relevant for these meters. The assessment of the accuracy class now centres on the handling of digital data streams from the current and voltage channels, which is mainly the performance of the energy meter's internal algorithms and their response to various wave shapes embedded in the SV streams. Experiments to underpin the accuracy of this kind of meter have been done before. In [1] two meters, conventional and digital, are compared in a real installed environment. Similar tests as described in this article have been described in [2]. Since there are no standards yet for the requirements on digital metering equipment, the tests described in the IEC 62053-22 [3] are followed, as far as they are applicable for a meter with digital inputs. In anticipation of the new standard, which will most likely carry the number IEC 62053-25, chapter 8 of IEC 62053-22 is of special interest for testing the energy meter, as it describes the accuracy test. Other chapters of IEC 62053-22 concern tests that are not directly relevant to the accuracy due to the digital nature of the device. These include tests like power consumption, overcurrent, heating, and self-heating.

II. IDENTIFICATION OF ERROR SOURCES

In contrast to analog meters, digital meters eliminate the need to account for current transformers, shunts, voltage dividers, and voltage references that might impact measurements. Referring to the schematic in Fig. 1, the only potential error sources identified in the meter itself are the algorithms processing the SVs on the internal processor and the clock

Fig. 1. Schematic of the digital energy meter, consisting of an internal clock, a micro-controller (MCU), display, and communication interfaces for both the IEC 61850-9-2 and the DLMS/COSEM.

providing the timing to this processor. Depending on the synchronization implementation in the digital meter, there is a possibility that the analogue clock reference could affect measurements.

Regarding these error sources, the harmonics and sub-harmonics tests from IEC 62053-22 are particularly useful as they reveal how the meter algorithms handle harmonic energy content. Also, tests with low power factor determine how well the algorithm can process reactive power. To discern timing errors from other errors, an extra test was designed since the IEC 62053-22 deals with analogue meters which do not have timing signals embedded in their voltage and current inputs. In this test, the clock of the SV stream is adjusted to deviate from the nominal frequency.

III. TEST SETUP

The test setup, see Fig. 2, has been designed for the absolute calibration of digital energy meters. To test digital energy meters, an SV stream must be generated. The generation of the SV stream is done by a generator consisting of a real-time processor that runs custom software. The SV stream generator is capable of generating various synthetic signals and embedding them in a data stream, following IEC 61850-9-2LE, that simulates a poly-phase grid. The signals can vary in amplitude, phase, frequency, and wave shape. The SV generator can generate an SV stream that contains an exact amount of energy. Within the IEC 61850-9-2 network, a precision time protocol (PTP) Grand Master was present, and a PTP-aware switch. If possible, the energy meter under test is synchronized to the PTP clock. The SV streams are propagated to the meter under test via a switch. A PC connected to the same

network controls the SV generator and captures the SV stream, to verify the data integrity. Traceable timing is achieved by synchronizing the SV stream to the PTP clock. Reading of the meter's instantaneous values is done through using the DLMS/COSEM protocol (IEC 62056-47 [4]) over ethernet. The SV stream generator is verified through post-processing of the packets captured by the PC. This post-processing step extracts voltage, current, and sample count information from the packets, checking for missing packets. From the voltage and current values, along with the sample rate, the energy of each packet is calculated. Summing the energy values of all the packets, the total energy present in the SV stream is found and verified against the SV stream generator settings. Verification demonstrates that, for a sample of 10 MWh (600 A, 100 kV, 50 Hz, 200 s, PF = 1, polyphase), the measured packets align with the settings within the uncertainties of the quantization errors of the SV voltage and current, surpassing the accuracy of 50 ppb.

IV. TESTING PROCEDURE AND FIRST RESULTS

At the start of a measurement, the current is set to zero, ensuring no energy is delivered, and a voltage is applied to make the meter enter its normal operation mode. After that, the meter registers are read through the DLMS/COSEM port on the meter to obtain all relevant information including the last energy count. Then the current is turned on for a fixed amount of samples, corresponding to a fixed amount of time. The current switching is performed smoothly over 1 second to suppress any switching artefacts. The smoothing is done with a cubic function that is flat at the start and end of the transition period. This ensures the derivative of the current with respect to time is never infinite. After the current has been switched off at the end of the measurement, the meter is read again. The difference between the energy stop reading and the start reading is taken as the energy measurement. This is done for different combinations of voltage, current, power factor, harmonic content, and integration time.

Initial tests in the presence of harmonics revealed errors that exceeded the class limits. Other meters that were connected to the same SV stream during the test did not show these errors, validating the proposed method.

Fig. 2. Schematic overview of the test setup for measuring the absolute error of a digital energy meter. The SV generator generates an SV stream which is measured by both the energy meter and the PC. Timing in the network is provided by a PTP server.

V. UNCERTAINTY

Four factors contributing to the uncertainty of digital energy meters have been identified: SV quantization, reported energy quantization, timing differences, and meter repeatability. SV quantization errors are inherent to the SV generator system. As per the IEC 61869-9 [5] standard, an SV stream employs 10 mV as the voltage quantum and 1 mA as the current quantum, both quantization errors following a rectangular distribution. Due to the cumulative nature of energy values, the impact of quantization errors on the measurement result diminishes with the square root of the number of samples. The reported energy quantization depends on the meter under test and the total energy presented to the meter. Long integration times may be required to keep the uncertainty contribution low enough to verify a meter meets the standard. Timing differences arise from the difference in the timing embedded in the SV stream and the internal time reference of the digital energy meter. If the meter derives the timing for its algorithms from the SV stream, there is no timing difference and no associated error.

VI. CONCLUSION

Even though the digital energy meter is a digital device it is still prone to errors and thus must be characterized. This could be done either by calibration or type testing if the error sources are repeatable. These errors exist in the algorithms processing the digital values and in the clock driving the processor. Our initial findings in digital energy meter calibrations show that most errors are caused by the resolution of the reported energy values. A notable exception is one meter that does not integrate energy contained in harmonics according to the standard. Also, our tests indicate that one meter uses its internal reference clock instead of the PTP clock or the time information embedded in the SV stream, which gives rise to errors when it deviates from the SV timing. Elaborate tests using the method described in this paper will be presented at the conference.

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